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Research Article

**A SURVEY FOR ASSESSING KNOWLEDGE ABOUT OTC
DRUGS AMONG COMMUNITY PHARMACISTS IN
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Article Received: July 2024**Accepted: July 2024****Published: August 2024****Abstract:**

Over-the-counter (OTC) medicines are drugs that can be sold without the prescription of a registered medical practitioner to the consumer. In India, over-the-counter medicines include analgesics, nutrients, cough and cold medications, and Ayurveda preparations. The unregulated or unrestricted availability of OTC drugs in the market increases the risks of drug resistance, adverse drug reactions, and drug interactions. OTC medicines are often used for self-medication by students for conditions such as fever, pain, and colds. Awareness regarding OTC drugs can lead to better medical practices and prevent any untoward medical occurrences. This paper assesses the knowledge of community pharmacists regarding over-the-counter medications in the southern part of Kerala. A pre- validated questionnaire was used after obtaining informed consent. Analysis was conducted using MS Excel. Analgesics, antipyretics, and anti allergic drugs were the most commonly used OTC drugs for coughs, common colds, and fevers by the people. Most of the community pharmacists were aware of over-the-counter medicines, but their knowledge regarding OTC medications was found to be poor. The present study indicates that the use of over-the-counter drugs is widespread; therefore, it is necessary to create awareness and educate people regarding the advantages and disadvantages of self-medication. Hence, our study underscores the need for conducting survey-based studies with the objective of evaluating the knowledge of community pharmacists.

KeyWords: Knowledge, Survey, Over the counter medicines, Self-medication, Adverse drug reaction.**INTRODUCTION**

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INTRODUCTION:

“Over-the-counter” (OTC) medicines are drugs that can be sold without the prescription of a registered medical practitioner. OTC drugs have no legal recognition in India; all drugs not included in the list of 'prescription-only drugs' are considered non-prescription drugs. The practice of purchasing and ingesting drugs without taking advice from a health professional is termed self-medication. OTC drugs are legally allowed to be sold 'over the counter' by pharmacists, meaning without the prescription of a registered medical practitioner. Prescription-only drugs are those medicines listed in Schedules H and X of the Drug and Cosmetics Rules.

Drugs listed in Schedule G (mostly antihistamines) don't need a prescription to purchase but require the following mandatory text on the label: 'Caution: It is dangerous to take this preparation except under medical supervision.' OTC drugs recognized as safe and effective and not misbranded are also available as OTC drugs in the market now (FDA). Unrestricted availability of OTC drugs in the market increases the risk of adverse drug reactions and drug interactions. Studies have reported an increased or potential risk of drug abuse with these products. Misuse of OTC drugs by consumers includes overuse and taking several drugs concurrently used to treat serious diseases. The use of OTC drugs as self-medication for conditions such as fever, stomach ache, body pain, cough, and cold is more common among undergraduate medical students.

Types of otc medications:

ANALGESICS

ANTIBIOTICS

COUGH SUPPRESSANTS

ANTI-ACNE DRUGS

NSAIDS (Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs)

ANTISEPTICS

DECONGESTANTS

ANTACIDS

ANTIFUNGALS

ANTI-HISTAMINES

SMOKING CESSATION DRUGS

Examples of some otc drugs and their indications:

Acyclovir : Antiviral

Brompheniramine : Antihistamine

Chlorpheniramine maleate : Antihistamine

Cholestyramine : Cholesterol-lowering drug

Cimetidine : Gastric acid reducer

Clemastine fumarate : Antihistamine

Colestipol : Cholesterol-lowering drug

Dexbrompheniramine maleate : Antihistamine

Diflunisal : Analgesic, antipyretic

Diphenhydramine HCl : Antihistamine, antitussive, sleep aid

Doxylamine succinate : Sleep aid

Dyclonine HCl : Oral local anesthetic, analgesic

Famotidine : Gastric ulcer reducer

Fluoride salts : Dental caries prophylaxis

Ibuprofen : Analgesic, antipyretic

Ketoprofen : Analgesic, antipyretic

Loperamide : Antidiarrheal

REASONS FOR USING OTC MEDICATIONS

- Shortage of time and comfort
- Cheaper in price
- Availability
- Level of literacy and awareness

Drug combinations	Effect	Management options/considerations
Aspirin and NSAIDs or multiple NSAIDs	Increased risk of serious GI complications. Risk increases with increased dose and number of agents	Avoid concurrent use of more than one NSAID, if possible. Consider adding gastroprotective agents
Anticoagulants and NSAIDs	Increased risk of bleeding (especially GI) and increased oral warfarin activity	Avoid concurrent use of NSAID; monitor prothrombin time and occult blood in urine and stool
Corticosteroids and NSAIDs	Increased GI side effects, including ulceration and hemorrhage	Avoid concurrent use of NSAID and consider adding a gastroprotective agent
SSRIs and NSAIDs	Increased risk of GI bleeding	Avoid concurrent use of NSAID
Aspirin and ibuprofen or naproxen	Reduced antiplatelet effects of aspirin	Not seen with other NSAIDs or acetaminophen
Antihypertensive agents and NSAIDs	Use of NSAIDs may increase blood pressure	Monitor blood pressure and cardiac function

OTC LABELS:

Counselling for otc products:

- Indication and dosage:
The pharmacist or healthcare provider should explain the indication for the product and the recommended dosage based on the patient's age, weight, and medical history.
- Potential side effects:
Patients should be informed of potential side effects associated with the product and advised on how to manage them.
- Precautions and warnings:
Patients should be advised on any precautions or warnings associated with the product, such as avoiding certain activities or foods while using the product.
- Interactions with other medications:
Patients should be advised on potential interactions between the product and other medications they may be taking, including prescription medications, OTC medications, and supplements.
- Duration of use:
Patients should be advised on the recommended duration of use for the product and when to seek

medical attention if symptoms persist or worsen.

METHODOLOGY:**Study project:**

The duration of study is for 6 months.

Study site:

It is the study conducted in community pharmacies in and around southern part of Kerala.

Study design:

This is a community based study where the pharmacist in the community where interviewed the knowledge about OTC drugs and data was collected and data analysis will be done.

Sample size:

61 Samples are selected randomly from the community pharmacies from the southern part of Kerala.

The sample size of the study is to calculated by the following formula

$$\text{Sample size (n)} = \frac{2\alpha^2 P(1-P)}{d^2}$$

α = The standard normal with α % level of significance.

P = Proportion of the knowledge about OTC drugs d = Margin of error or precision of the study.

From the literature review the properties of the survey for assessing knowledge about OTC is 80% with a margin of error or precision as 10% and the level of significance is 5%.

Then the estimated sample size for the study is

$$\text{Sample size (n)} = \frac{2\alpha^2 P(1-P)}{d^2} = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.80 \times 0.20}{(0.10)^2}$$

=61 samples needed for the study.

Study procedure:

A survey is conducted for assessing the knowledge about OTC drugs among community pharmacists in southern part of Kerala. A written informed consent is taken from pharmacist about dispensing OTC drugs. All information relevant to study was collected from direct interview with pharmacist. A demographic characters, knowledge about dispensing of OTC drugs is documented in the Proforma.

A structured interview with pharmacist was conducted by using questionnaire to elicit information about dispensing OTC drugs. In this study a survey was conducted to assess the knowledge among community pharmacist to OTC related aspects.

The knowledge about community pharmacists were assessed by using suitably designed questionnaire prior to survey. The questionnaire that contains total 15 questions. The information was collected from 61 Pharmacies among Southern part of Kerala. The knowledge part contains YES or NO questions.

Data entry and analysis:

After getting the data will be analysed and suitably tabulated, formulated and presented.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Pranit P.Gayakar, Rahul S.Adnaik, Amit D.Jadhav, Shrinivas K. Mohite et al conducted a survey of knowledge about OTC drugs among pharmacy background and non-pharmacy community, published in the year 2016. This study was conducted to assess the knowledge about OTC drugs among pharmacy background and non-pharmacy community. From the conducted survey it can be concluded that there is need of creating awareness about knowledge of otc medications among various categories of community. Especially in the rural area the orientation programmes are need to be conducted which can be helpful in reducing misuse and to elicit proper use of OTC medications.

Shiv kumar, Jintu John et al conduct the assessment of Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of OTC drugs among community pharmacists, published in the year 2021. It is a sustainable fact that OTC use is not illegal, but it might be associated with safety and other issues and may lead to potential

health hazards. The findings of the study showed that the majority of the CPs had basic knowledge regarding OTC drugs, but practice of clinical pharmacy profession needs to be improved. It is recommended that the need for health educational interventions such as pamphlets and awareness programs about the hazards of misusing drugs targeting both the general public as well as CPs thereby promoting the appropriate use of drugs. Hence the study concludes that improving pharmacist KAP about OTC can improve the rational use of non-prescription drugs.

Paxton and chapple et al conducted a study to establish the number and kinds of people affected by OTC medicine misuse, medicines involved, pharmacist concerned and policies, published in the year 1996. This was concluded that the literature relating to OTC medicine abuse has revealed that there is a recognized problem internationally involving a range of medicine and potential harms. Such research is needed to inform policy, regulation and the preparedness of a range of healthcare professionals to avoid harm to those who purchase OTC medicines that may be liable to abuse.

D.Indra Kumary, S. Jayakumari, E. Padhma Priya, J. Abel Joe Jacob et al conduct a study, shows that knowledge, attitude & performance of the community pharmacist's in prescribing OTC medicines in the field of acute pain management were GOOD. And also the study concludes that there is adequate knowledge regarding the applications of OTC drugs used for the treatment of acute pain. Therefore, Training programs such as educational pamphlets & continuing educational seminars may play important roles in increasing pharmacist's knowledge & therefore improving their performance in prescribing OTC medicines.

Abinaya Ravichandran, Asha Basavareddy et al conduct the study to assess knowledge, Attitude & Practice of the pharmacist towards dispensing the OTC medications. The study has concluded that majority of the pharmacists were qualified to dispense medication, but only few knew about OTC drugs. Analgesics were most commonly used OTC. These drugs were safe to dispense, however, consulting doctor before taking medications was suggested by some of them.

**OBSERVATION AND RESULT:
RESULT FROM QUESTIONNAIRE:**

DISPENSING OF OTC DRUGS

PHARMACIST DISPENSE OTC	BEFORE COUNSELLING		AFTER COUNSELLING	
	FREQUENCY (n=61)	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUENCY (n=61)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	61	100	61	100
No	0	0	0	0

The result is not statistically significant because in the before and after counselling are same.

Pharmacists dispensing antibiotics as otc:

DISPENSE ANTIBIOTICS AS OTC	BEFORE COUNSELLING		AFTER COUNSELLING	
	FREQUENCY (n=61)	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUENCY (n=61)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	13	21.31	5	8.19
No	48	78.68	56	91.80

There is a statistically significant difference between the before and after counselling the p- value is .041, which is less than .05

Pharmacists advice about the use, side effects & adr:

ADVICES ABOUT USE, SIDE EFFECTS & ADR	BEFORE COUNSELLING		AFTER COUNSELLING	
	FREQUENCY (n=61)	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUENCY (n=61)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	23	37.70	48	78.68
No	38	62.29	13	21.31

There is a statistically significant difference between the before and after counselling the p- value is .001, which is less than .05

Counselling of products before dispensing otc drugs by pharmacists:

COUNSELING BEFORE DISPENSING OTC DRUGS	BEFORE COUNSELLING		AFTER COUNSELLING	
	FREQUENCY (n=61)	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUENCY (n=61)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	21	34.42	39	63.93
No	40	65.57	22	36.06

There is a statistically significant difference between the before and after counselling the p- value is .042, which is less than .05

COUNSELLING SCORE:

BEFORE COUNSELLING			PERCENTAGE	AFTER COUNSELLING			PERCENTAGE
0 -5	BELOW AVERAGE	8	13.11	0 -5	BELOW AVERAGE	3	4.9
5 -10	AVERAGE	42	68.8	5 -10	AVERAGE	27	44.2
10 -15	EXCELLENT	11	18.03	10 -15	EXCELLENT	31	50.8

- For below average ,there is no significant difference,p-value is .114, which is greater than .05
- For average score, there is statistically significant difference ,p- value is .006, which is less than .05
- For excellent score, there is statistically significant difference p-value is .001, which is less than .05

DISCUSSION:

The survey is conducted in southern part of Kerala among the community Pharmacist in order to check the knowledge OR information about OTC drugs. The present study was a questionnaire- based study which included community Pharmacists from southern part of Kerala. This is the first study in the southern part of Kerala that evaluated the knowledge of community Pharmacists regarding OTC – related aspects.

This study aims to assess the knowledge of community Pharmacists regarding OTC – related aspects. A total of 61 community pharmacies were included in the survey, which utilized a questionnaire method for assessment.

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CONCLUSION:

Based on the conducted survey to assess the knowledge of OTC drugs among community pharmacists, initially, the average knowledge level about OTC drugs was determined. Subsequently, leaflets and counselling were provided to raise awareness about OTC drugs. The survey concluded that although there was an improvement in knowledge, after counselling, this improvement was statistically significant.

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